

EnergyMeasures

Tailored measures supporting energy vulnerable households

D6.7

Main communications and dissemination materials (part 2)

 <http://www.energymeasures.eu>

 @NRGMeasures

February 2024

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 894759

Document Information

Deliverable ID	6.7		
Deliverable Title	Main communications and dissemination materials part 2		
Lead beneficiary	OKP		
Contributing beneficiaries	all		
Due date Annex I	2024.02.29		
Issue date	2024.02.29		
Dissemination level	Public		
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Document checked	Niall Dunphy	Date:	2024.02.29

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The EnergyMeasures Project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 894759. For more information on the project, its partners, and contributors please see <http://www.energymeasures.eu>.

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About EnergyMeasures

EnergyMEASURES is working to address energy poverty in seven European countries, namely: Belgium, Bulgaria, Ireland, Netherlands, North Macedonia, Poland and the United Kingdom. The project comprises two complementary and synergistic strands of work.

The first strand involves working with energy poor households to improve their energy efficiency through a combination of low-cost measures, and changes in energy-related behaviours and practices. Recruited householders will be provided with low-cost energy measures and empowered to change their energy-related behaviours and practices through an approach that takes account of existing housing conditions and is reflective of their lived experience.

The second strand comprises working with municipalities, energy authorities, housing associations and other relevant actors to assess how current multi-level institutional contexts affect efforts to alleviate energy vulnerability in the participating countries. This knowledge will be used to develop and support the implementation of policy and practice measures which will address structural issues that combine to trap households in energy poverty.

Through this work the project contributes to reducing participants' vulnerability to energy poverty, while at the same time cutting household energy consumption and associated GHG emissions.

For more information see <http://www.energymeasures.eu>

Description of the deliverable and its purpose

This deliverable provides an overview of the Communication (T6.1) and Dissemination (T6.2) activities of the EnergyMeasures project that have been completed over the past 24 months (March 2022 to February 2024). The purpose of this deliverable, in the form of a report, is to summarize the materials and formats developed in WP6 to achieve the Key Performance Indicators applicable to all Communication and Dissemination Activities outlined in the description of action as well as in the Communication and Dissemination Strategy (D.6.2, submitted in Nov. 2020). Deliverable 6.7 is to be read complementary to the second and final iteration of Deliverable 6.5 “Final Communication and Dissemination report”.

Glossary

WP	Work Package
D/Del.	Deliverable
DoA	Description of Action
OKP	Oikoplus GmbH
UCC	University College Cork

1 Communication and Dissemination Background

The objectives of the Work Package as well as the essential steps to achieve these objectives are specified in the DoA:

“The objective of this work package is to maximise the impact of EnergyMEASURES, by achieving the maximum awareness of the project and its results among stakeholders in fuel poverty and consumer behaviour change, and disseminating the best practice methods for engagement of energy poor citizens developed during the project. The WP includes two main areas of work:

- *Communications plan to ensure the widest possible awareness of the project its outputs;*
- *Dissemination strategy to ensure the outputs and lessons from the project contribute to change in policy and practices in tackling energy poverty.” (DoA, p.25)*

A detailed description of the selected communication approach was provided in the Communication Plan (D6.2) submitted in Project Month 3 (November 2020).

At the beginning of the project, the communicative task was to provide the project with a visual identity that was as distinctive as possible and to set up and populate the various communication channels to support household recruitment. For the second half of the project, the focus was on communicating results and findings, aligning with cognate projects, and providing relevant stakeholders with applied knowledge and policy advice to alleviate energy poverty and/or define strategies to support energy-vulnerable households.

Since the beginning of the project, Oikoplus (OKP) as lead beneficiary of WP6 has pursued the strategy to involve the other partner organisations in the EnergyMeasures project as actively as possible in communication and dissemination. This early involvement helped to build a project legacy were all partners feel invited to proactively contribute to communication and dissemination and lasted towards the project end. The legacy build in this context led to communication and dissemination outcomes valid for training and dissemination workshops as well as for policy recommendations tailored to needs at the local and/or national level, as well as for cooperation in communication and dissemination at the supranational level. OKP has therefore taken on the role of a provider of communication materials, providing the other consortium partners with materials for communication, to be translated into national languages and adapted to local conditions and communication requirements.

2 Compendium of materials designed to support the overall communication and dissemination efforts from Mar 2022 to Feb 2024

In addition to materials, which primarily serve to communicate the project partners in their countries, OKP has also crafted the results and findings of the project into various communication materials suitable for different channels.

2.1.1 Project Website

The project website has been the central communication channel for EnergyMeasures since the beginning of the project. With the basic functionality and technical setup of the website in October 2020, the website and its sub-sites have been continuously updated. Major updates and extensions are discussed in the following subsections.

2.1.1.1 Regular contributions

Blog posts have been written at regular intervals to keep the website up to date. A detailed list of the blog posts produced and published under the '[News](#)' section can be found in D6.5 "Final Communication and dissemination report". The content of the blog posts reflects the reorganisation of the communication strategy for the second half of the project. This means that in addition to updates on meetings, the results of the project have also been reported. A total of 42 blog posts have been published since the start of the project.

2.1.1.2 Step-by-step guidelines for Behaviour Change

Based on a workshop at the General Assembly in Krakow to identify different approaches to behaviour change in the context of energy poverty, and building on the results discussed in D1.2 "Guidelines for integrating behaviour change approaches while engaging energy poor" and D4.3 "Initial report on behaviour change initiatives among energy poor households", Oikoplus formulated and programmed a series of steps in the summer of 2023, which are primarily intended to help energy advisors to better assess their clients' energy consumption in a first step and to reduce it in a second step in the long term and as part of behaviour change. The corresponding [step-by-step](#) guidelines are available on the homepage.

ENERGYMEASURES Home News Regions + Step-by-Step Guidelines Work Plan Project Outputs About +

Step-by-Step Guidelines

As part of the ongoing project, we are proposing some steps that can help the energy consumption advisors understand people's energy usage better and help them inform consumers about their options when choosing a certain energy consumption strategy. We tackle information on behavioural change and its importance on the subject on energy poverty, as well as a step-by-step guideline on how to help integrate behaviour change approaches while engaging energy poor within the EnergyMeasures project. While the guideline was developed by [Dunphy et al. \(2020\)](#), we also took the liberty of adding some examples of how these approaches fared locally in in partnering countries, as well as some tips on behavioural change evaluation

How to identify energy vulnerable households

While energy poverty can have multiple causes, we firstly need to define it and its possible manifestations. This article is looking at a general explanation of what energy poverty is and what subsequent problems that leads to.

The behaviour change approach

Even though many people might think that they are behaving in an energy-saving, efficient way the truth might be otherwise. This article explains how behavioural change is a crucial part of improving energy consumption habits.

Guidelines for implementing change in energy poor households

After identifying habits leading to energy poverty and understanding how to change these, this article looks at 5 guidelines that energy advisors need to keep in mind when engaging with people living in energy poor households.

Figure 1: Step-by-step Guidelines on the EnergyMeasures website.

2.1.1.3 Policy briefs

A new automatically rotating sub-section "Executive Summaries" has been created under "[Project outputs](#)". All executive summaries displayed in this section have been created to extend the publicly available outputs in a more accessible short form. A total of 14 briefing papers of maximum two pages have been produced to facilitate access to the knowledge published in the outputs through short introductions with highlights and bullet points. All the policy briefs were also printed and distributed at the final EnergyMeasures conference.

Figure 2: Carousel of Policy Briefs/Executive Summaries on the Energy Measures website.

2.1.2 Newsletter

A regular newsletter has been published throughout the project. A total of 5 newsletters have been published since the start of the project. Each newsletter contains an editorial, in-depth coverage of the latest deliverables and an overview of what is currently happening in the project. The last newsletter was published and distributed in February 2024.

The newsletters were distributed via contacts linked to Mailchimp and via the channels of the project partners.

2.1.3 Social Media Channels

In addition to the website, its sub-websites and national landing pages, OKP has been running social media channels for the EnergyMeasures project on X (1035 posts), Instagram (122 posts; 7 pinned reels linked to specific topics) and Facebook (48 videos, 120 photos/stills and occasional text-based posts) since the start of the project, where editorial content is regularly distributed.

Figure 3: Pinned reels on the EnergyMeasures Instagram Account

Figure 4: Thumbnails from video campaign launched on Facebook in April 2023

2.1.4 Project videos

In the second part of the project communication, as the recruitment of households in several member states had already been completed and the focus was now on a result-oriented approach, it made sense to communicate the challenges, approaches, and results of the project more strongly in video format. In addition to the planning, implementation, production and post-production of expert interviews from the project, it is worth mentioning in particular the videos which – in addition to the small measures applied in EnergyMeasures – also attempted to show the diversity and complexity of energy poverty. With the support of local project partners, the OKP produced short documentaries on energy poverty in Turnhout (Belgium), Bielsko-Biala (Poland) and Stornoway (United Kingdom). The videos feature people affected by energy poverty as well as local actors who in one way or another contribute to reducing energy poverty. All short films have been published on the various channels operated by EnergyMeasures and used for project communication. The last video to be made available to the public was a recording of the [Panel discussion at the Final EnergyMeasures Conference in Brussels](#) on 17 January 2024.

2.1.5 Project documentary

Among the many video productions, one deserves special mention: the EnergyMeasures Documentary. This 25-minute documentary uses footage from selected partner countries to provide a holistic view of the complexity of energy poverty and the challenges it poses.

The project documentary is available on [YouTube](#) and on the project website. The first public screening of the EnergyMeasures Documentary was at the Final EnergyMeasures conference in January 2024. Accompanying measures were undertaken to promote the EnergyMeasures documentary across channels.

Figure 5: EnergyMeasures documentary on YouTube

Figure 6: Documentary Promotion on X

2.1.6 EnergyMeasures Book Publication

Living with EnergyPoverty: Perspectives from the Global North and South is the central academic publication produced as part of EnergyMeasures and was published as in paper and e-book formats by Routledge Taylor & Francis on 1 December 2023. Curated by Paola Velasco-Herrejón, Breffní Lennon and Niall P. Dunphy, the publication brings together contributions from different parts of the world, all dealing with energy poverty. The publication is divided into three parts; Part 1 deals with concepts and methodologies, Part 2 focuses on stories and narratives from everyday life; and Part 3 deals with the concept of energy poverty in policy recommendations and sustainability courses.

Chapter 1: The Global Face of Energy Poverty; Chapter 2 Identifying Energy-Poor Households, Experiences from the Global North; and Chapter 22: Towards a Better Understanding of Energy Poverty are freely available under Creative Commons Licence 4.0 (CC-BY-NC-ND). A [paperback version](#) of the book can be purchased from the publisher’s website.

Figure 6: Book Cover

Figure 7: Routledge Taylor & Francis Online Bookstore

3 Compendium of materials produced to support partners' communication and dissemination efforts from Mar 2022 to Feb 2024

3.1.1 EUSEW Submission and Sustainable Energy Week Flyer PNEC

At the suggestion of Oikoplus, various project partners (including the coordinator) prepared a submission for the European Sustainable Energy Week 2023. It was suggested that a stand be set up to present results from the household engagement programme as well as policy recommendations. Unfortunately, the stand was not nominated by the organisers of the European Sustainable Energy Week.

In addition to the submission for the stand at the EUSEW, a folder on energy saving tips and three flyers promoting energy efficiency for a corresponding high-level meeting, including public relations work, was designed as part of local activities and in cooperation with other projects (including the Polish Energy Poverty Hub Advisory Board).

Figure 8: Three different posters designed to promote EnergyMeasures-supported EUSEW Activities at the Geovita Training Centre in Jadwisin, Poland

Card Game Translation

On November 22, 2021 (project month 15), a deck of cards on Energy Poverty / Energy Vulnerability was provided to partners for translation into local languages.

4 Workshop and Event Formats Implemented by Project

4.1.1 Project workshops, events and conference visibility

A large part of the visibility of the project was directly related to the numerous workshops that were organised over the course of its timeframe. The events and conferences addressed a wide range of stakeholders. Details on the stakeholders reached during the events can be found in D6.5 "Final Communication and Dissemination Report".

From the point of view of the communication and dissemination materials used, it is only necessary to mention here that the above-mentioned events utilised the project branding that has been used consistently since the beginning of the project. The main focus was on the [EnergyMeasures presentation template](#) that Oikoplus provided to the partners at the beginning of the project and has remained unchanged since then.

4.1.2 Final Event

4.1.2.1 Format

On 17 January 2024 at 16:00, EnergyMeasures hosted its final conference at Atelier29 in Rue Jacques de Lalaing in Brussels, Belgium. The title of the event was "EnergyMeasures: supporting households address energy poverty". The event itself provided ample time for input, formal and informal exchanges.

Agenda:

16:00-16:25 Welcome and opening remarks

16:25-16:50 Tailored Measures Supporting Energy vulnerable Households (Documentary)

16:50-17:15 Highlights from the EnergyMeasures project

17:15-18:30 Panel discussion: Living with energy poverty

18:30-19:30 Networking reception

4.1.2.2 Invitation Management

Invitations to the event were sent out through various channels, including partner newsletters and over partners' and the EnergyMeasures project's social media channels. A number of people were contacted directly by email. Registrations were made via an [event on the Eventbrite platform](#), which was used for all event management. On the day of the event, we counted over 33 registrations on Eventbrite, mainly from people outside the project.

The first announcements, including the title and location of the event, were sent out a month before the event in the form of a save-the-date.

Figure 9: EnergyMeasures Final conference Registration via Eventbrite

4.1.2.3 Roll-ups and Supporting Materials

Oikoplus took accompanying measures for the event. In addition to branded presentations and background screens, the venue was branded with posters and roll-ups.

Figure 10: Examples of EnergyMeasures posters and roll ups designed for Final Conference

4.1.2.4 Post-Conference Procedures

Following the final conference, several measures were taken to keep the results accessible and available. Firstly, the full version of the panel discussion was made available online on YouTube. A report in the form of a blog post titled "[Illuminating Perspectives: Panel discussion on Tackling Energy Poverty](#)" and a [press](#)

[release](#) on the successful organisation of a final evening event were posted online immediately after the event. The EnergyMeasures Final Conference was also featured in [Newsletter No. 5](#).

A blog post inspired by the EnergyMeasures Final Conference was also published in the Domino-E project news section. The article titled "[Applying Earth Observation: Energy Poverty](#)" focuses on the contribution that satellite-based Earth observation can make, or will soon be able to make, to reducing energy poverty in Europe and worldwide.

5 Press releases

Over the course of the project, Oikoplus and UCC, as well as other project partners, repeatedly sent out press releases to support the communication and dissemination work. The press releases sent out directly by the project can be found in the "[News](#)" section of the homepage.

Figure 11: Carousel of Press Releases on EnergyMeasures Website

6 Partner channels

It was already clear in the first half of the project that the project partners had a valuable communication skillset and connections with respect especially to engaging with households. The value of their communication channels was further demonstrated with their outreach to practitioners, policymakers and politicians. These actors are emphasised in [D3.2 "Energy Poverty Policy Agenda and Recommendations"](#) as playing an extremely important role in the fight against energy poverty, not least as an important link between citizens, companies, and supra-regional decision-makers.

Although, most of the project partners did not require additional support from the designated communication partner for communication at the regional level, Oikoplus did provide support as needed. Regular exchange within the consortium and the opportunity to ask questions was usually enough to support the project partners with their communications needs on the ground.